

REGIONAL DEVELOPMENT THROUGH CLUSTERS

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Abstract

Purpose – *At the level of global market competition, the economic success of a region or country focuses on the specialization of supply, the development of key areas, offering competitive advantages, skills and qualified resources. From this perspective, clusters are the key to success, involving entrepreneurial dynamism, intense links between organizations and institutions with top-level knowledge.*

Methodology/approach – *Accentuating the phenomenon of globalization and increasing competitiveness in national, European and international markets, membership in a cluster becomes a real advantage for small and medium enterprises, providing easy access to production, innovative products, using advanced technologies, common development strategies.*

Findings – *The most important role of a cluster is to facilitate development, having as success factors: building trust between cluster members and creating a cluster development strategy, the geographical proximity of cluster members.*

Research limitations/implications – *The clusters support the transfer of know-how and technology transfer, cooperation between companies and institutions and the importance of strengthening the support environment.*

Practical implications – *The ability to innovate in the business environment is a key factor for increasing competitiveness and for smart and sustainable development. The innovation process contributes more and more to local-regional and national development.*

Originality/value – *Clusters are the pillars for smart, sustainable inclusion growth, facilitating and creating jobs, improving cooperation between business, research institutes, universities and other organizations based on increasing competitiveness, labor specialization, regional development.*

Key words: *cluster, human capital, competitiveness.*

Introduction

At the level of global market competition, the economic success of a region or country focuses on the specialization of supply, the development of key areas, offering competitive advantages, skills and qualified resources. From this perspective, clusters are the key to success, involving entrepreneurial dynamism, intense links between organizations and institutions with top-level knowledge.

Accentuating the phenomenon of globalization and increasing competitiveness in national, European and international markets, membership in a cluster becomes a real advantage for small and medium enterprises, providing easy access to production, innovative products, using advanced technologies, common development strategies.

The most important role of a cluster is to facilitate development, having as success factors: building trust between cluster members and creating a cluster development strategy, the geographical proximity of cluster members.

Currently, in the North-West Region of Romania there are 7 active clusters, in the fields of wood industry, renewable energy, agriculture, IT, services, generating successful business in this region, which are presented in detail in this research.

Clusters support the transfer of know-how and technology transfer, cooperation between companies and institutions and the importance of strengthening the support environment. At national level, 6 are members of CLUSTERO - Romanian Association of Clusters, from those analyzed in this paper.

In the report we identified examples of good national and international practice in the field of clusters, highlighting the diversity of multiple ways of applying the cluster concept. Cluster implementation reports lead to transformations of opportunities and determinants with positive effects on smart, regionally sustainable development. We tried to analyze the situation in Romania of clusters and their development factors, such as the involvement of specialized human resources, identifying trends and development prospects at national and regional level, promoting examples of good practice based on the Europe 2020 Strategy. It can be said as an essential role on the processes of economic and social competitiveness, creating the premises for sustainable development, reducing the gaps between regions, but also the creative, innovative potential of the component resources. To achieve this stage of intermediate research, we considered ensuring a solid foundation of research, by studying the literature and using relevant publications included in the main flow of publications, identifying and analyzing best practices at national, international and analysis to the extent that some of these experiences can be adapted later to the national and regional specifics, performing a more rigorous radiography of the situation in Romania with appropriate projections in the regional plan, to identify areas with clustering potential. In the context of the studied topics, the successful examples are a real source of knowledge and information.

The Romanian Cluster Association is one of the most well-known organizations at national level. It aims to support and encourage the development of clusters, playing an important role in facilitating interactions between national clusters.

The complex and interdisciplinary nature of the research required the use of cluster research, both qualitative and quantitative, in the study of clusters.

The ability to innovate in the business environment is a key factor for increasing competitiveness and for smart and sustainable development. The innovation process contributes more and more to local-regional and national development. Partnerships made in the form of clusters have a positive effect on reducing disparities between regions, as well as in achieving economic convergence and developing smart specialization strategies for cluster development, thus accelerating the differentiation and emergence of structural change towards a knowledge-based economy.

Increasing the quality and competitiveness of organizations by developing quality training programs and resources, identifying ways to manage time, active participation in lifelong learning and effective communication makes it possible to strengthen the business environment at European standards.

The information and globalization era demands an open attitude towards human capacities for understanding and interacting with an increasingly complex and challenging world.

Regional development clusters

The role of regional policy in implementing the Europe 2020 strategy in the field of smart development, promoting innovation, offers complementarity between EU, national and regional support for innovation, research and development, entrepreneurship and information and communication technology.

By creating favorable conditions for innovation, education and research, encouraging, research and development, investments with a high degree of knowledge and orientation towards activities with higher added value. [Cosnita, 2010]. Thus, regional policy can contribute to the successful approach to the challenge - the region, to increase the capacity for innovation, research and development in enterprises and to strengthen the links they have with universities and research centers. Regions play a central role, as they are the main institutional partners for universities, other research and education institutions and SMEs, which are the key to the innovation process, making them an indispensable part of the Europe 2020 strategy.

The knowledge and innovation capacity of the regions depends on a multitude of factors, including: entrepreneurial culture, workforce skills, education and training institutions, innovation support services, technology transfer mechanisms, research infrastructure and development and ICT, researcher mobility,

business incubators, new sources of funding and local creative potential. Research and development and innovation performance varies widely within the EU.

Direct investment flows in recent years have been concentrated where they have found skilled labor, capital, experience, business traditions, specialist suppliers, capital institutions and competitive research institutes, as well as adequate infrastructure. [Dudian, 2011]. The positive results of these interconnections are related to skilled labor, reduced travel costs, transfer of know-how, availability, making it circulate both vertically through the number of sellers and buyers, and horizontally through complementary products and services.

Within the NW region, the economy has experienced a natural development trend. The economy of the region has the characteristics of an emerging economy in development, with an average share of services, GDP / VABR growing, a large number of enterprises compared to the national average, but small compared to the European average, relatively intense foreign activity, increasing investment attractiveness.

There are intelligence-intensive economic sectors that use specialized and skilled labor, such as creative industries, information technology, scientific and technical activities, which encourage innovation in all fields, thus identifying new sources of growth. [Nicolescu, 2015].

From the point of view of economic specialization, in terms of financial indicators, those related to human resources, industrial agglomerations and the potential to generate high added value, the main sectors of regional importance for the North-West Region were identified as: industry food, textile and clothing, wood and furniture, road transport vehicle industry, IT&C, creative industries, construction materials industry. These areas have the potential to generate high value-added products through concerted investments according to the smart specialization strategy. Having a real associative potential, in five of these fields the clusters were set up which, in addition to supporting the sector in which they operate, also fulfill the role of regional promoters.

Low labor productivity and the share of labor and resource intensive sectors to the detriment of those with high added value are the biggest weaknesses of the regional economic system. The industries in the North-West Region have, in addition to the relatively low added value, a low technological content, and their development is based on the cheap cost of labor and on imported materials.

Polycentric territorial development, the existence of a relatively well-developed business support infrastructure and the functional specialization given by the sectors with proven economic performances can contribute to attracting investments for capitalizing on the potential of domestic resources.

The North-West Region will have to act on the factors that determine the increase of productivity, respectively in the direction of increasing investments in physical and human capital, in the sectoral structure of the economy, in improving infrastructure, innovation capacity and R&D activities, entrepreneurship, public policies. . [Nicolescu, 2015].

Figure 1. Composition of clusters in the North-West region
Source: own processing

Contributions regarding the study and analysis of the factors of human capital development on the competitiveness of the clusters from the North-West of Romania

Research studies in the field have analyzed the links between human capital development and the competitiveness of clusters worldwide, European, but there are a small number of studies in this regard regarding the level of Romania, and especially at the level of the North-West development region.

The general objective of the research focuses on analyzing the existing links between specialized human capital, the study and evaluation of investment factors in human capital within industrial clusters, in the context of increasing competitiveness in the North-West development region of Romania.

This requires deepening the study of the impact that the development of human resources has on obtaining high performances within the Romanian clusters, but also the influence of the cluster relations on the human capital within them.

In Romania, the clusters were formed spontaneously, as a result of international projects, given that there was no policy to stimulate the formation of competitive productive agglomerations.

Research on clusters, so far has focused on the connection between specialized human capital (training, education, qualification, training), relationships within clusters (management, procurement, sales, technology, innovation) performance of the organization (productivity, low costs, quality, innovation).

The processing, analysis of the obtained data and interpretation of the research results were performed using the following programs: SPSS 20.0 (Statistical Packages for the Social Sciences).

The method of data collection is the survey, and the tool used is the questionnaire, which was applied to the representatives of the clusters set up in the North-West region in various fields of activity.

In order to perform a detailed analysis in the evolution of the resultant variables, using statistical-econometric models, we will use multiple linear regression. In terms of this multiple linear regression, the degree of contribution of each factor involved in the process of obtaining the expected effect can be analyzed.

Using the Whard method, the dendogram was performed, on which occasion the factors that have a high influence on increasing competitiveness were established, resulting in the fact that the most influential factors in the category of regional development are the market, environment and organization and in the category of increasing competitiveness. are the satisfaction of the human resource, the motivation, the quality of the offered service and the innovation / creativity.

The factors influencing the development of human resources within clusters will have to be correlated with performance based on additional quantitative information, which influences the efficiency of human capital, a multivariate analysis of human capacity, resources, competitive advantage and the relationship between them.

In order to be able to perform an analysis of cluster development factors in terms of human capital, it was considered the most relevant to apply a questionnaire, in order to perform qualitative analysis, in the North-West development region of Romania, taking into account the definition of the problem. , planning the research project, formulating the hypotheses, reviewing the specialized literature, elaborating the items of the questionnaire, building the questionnaire, pretesting the questionnaire, administering the questionnaire to the target group.

The analysis of the hypotheses through the prism of the SPSS 20.00 program led to the following correlations:

1. There is a positive influence between knowledge management and human capital efficiency.

This hypothesis came true, Linear correlation coefficient = 0.290 Sig = 0.000 which shows that there is a positive influence from knowledge management and human capital efficiency, but of lower intensity because this coefficient has a lower value. This conclusion is also supported by the graph below, where we find a small grouping of points on the diagonal.

Figure 2. The point cloud that shows the distribution of companies according to the efficiency of human capital, knowledge management and the type of cluster

Source: own processing

2. There is a positive influence between increasing the efficiency of human capital and the effects within the organization

The hypothesis was accepted, Linear correlation coefficient = 0.223 Sig = 0.001, which shows that there is a positive influence from the effects within the organization and the efficiency of human capital, but of lower intensity because this coefficient has a lower value. This conclusion is also supported by the graph below, where we find a small grouping of points on the diagonal.

Figure 3. The point cloud that shows the distribution of companies depending on the efficiency of human capital, the effects within organizations and the type of cluster

Source: own processing

3. There is a positive influence between increasing efficiency and increasing employee performance

Linear correlation coefficient = 0.188 Sig = 0.007 which demonstrates that there is a positive influence between increasing the efficiency of human capital and increasing employee performance, but of lower intensity because this coefficient has a lower value. The value of Sig allows us to state the existence of this influence even with a significance threshold of 1%.

Figure 4. The point cloud that shows the distribution of companies depending on the efficiency of human capital, increasing employee performance and the type of cluster.

Source: own processing

4. There is a positive influence between the frequency of situations in the organization and the results of the investment in human resources

Linear correlation coefficient = 0.484 Sig = 0.000 which demonstrates that there is a positive link between the frequency of situations in the organization and the results of investment in human resources, the connection quite strong given the value of the correlation coefficient and sig. This conclusion is also supported by the image below where we observe the grouping of the points around the main diagonal and the high concentration of the points towards high values of the two variables.

Figure 5. The point cloud that shows the distribution of companies according to the results of the investment in human resources, the frequency of situations in the organization and the type of cluster

Source: own processing

5. There is a positive influence between the dissemination of knowledge and the increase of employee performance

The hypothesis was accepted, Linear correlation coefficient = 0.397 Sig = 0.000, which demonstrates that there is a positive and medium intensity influence between the dissemination of knowledge and the increase of employee performance. This demonstrates that in the case of companies where there is a constant concern in disseminating knowledge, they expect an increase in employee performance. This idea is also supported by the chart below where we find that companies in which employee knowledge management is included in the organization's strategy, employee performance is higher.

Figure 6. The point cloud that shows us the distribution of companies according to the increase of employee performance, knowledge dissemination and cluster type

Source: own processing

Conclusions

It can be said that regional development through the prism of clusters brings the development of infrastructure, labor, cities, business, the formation of a network that eliminates certain costs, but with continuous investment and implement projects that bring benefits to both the development of the organization with the necessary endowments, but also the improvement of the human resource through exchanges of experience and participation in training courses, all leading to competitiveness, innovation, performance, increase of productivity.

From the analysis of the resulting data, by grouping the items on a number of 5 clusters, it is found that the companies are open to the external environment, which thus denotes an improvement of the managerial style in order to pay more and more attention to both the external environment. as well as to the parties involved.

At the same time, this research study can be used as an educational informative guide among the existing regional clusters at national and implicitly regional level, clusters formed by large zonal representatives of national and global corporations, which carry out their activity at the level of the analyzed research area. by new members and for opening the thinking horizon of newcomers, being thus at least a very useful didactic and educational analysis material, accessible to all and in an accessible manner, only the most important thing is to have the will to access and analyze.

The ability to innovate in the business environment is a key factor for increasing competitiveness and for smart and sustainable development. The innovation process contributes more and more to local-regional and national development.

In the case of this scientific research, the analyzes conducted led to the outline of the existing situation in the North-West development region of Romania, regarding the existence/ non-existence of a link between investment activities in human capital and the performance of selected clusters.

By cluster analysis it is desired that the entire data collection be divided into a collection of homogeneous groups, to analyze the influence of classified variables, depending on the influence and the smallest distance between them, respectively to classify objects according to groups homogeneous.

In the light of this paper, we highlighted the need to create clusters in as many counties of the region, especially in areas where it does not exist, generating added value to this region, providing a favorable framework for economic recovery in this dark period existing at national level. as well as globally.

Through the methods applied in the analysis of the importance of human capital on organizations, it can be said that human resource development programs make possible a professional retraining, in-depth training in a field, adaptation to new information technologies that provide dynamism to the cluster and increase profitability.

This paper is in line with the conference, as it aims to explore the challenges within clusters that influence business performance at the regional, national and global levels in step with new information, educational technologies and a more prosperous environment.

Clusters are the pillars for smart, sustainable inclusion growth, facilitating and creating jobs, improving cooperation between business, research institutes, universities and other organizations based on increasing competitiveness, labor specialization, regional development.

References

Cosniță D., Guth M.

2010

"Clusters and Potential Clusters in Romania - A Mapping Exercise"

Dudian M.

2011

"Innovative clusters: the case of Romania", București

Nicolescu O., Nicolescu C., Truică A., Urîtu D., Corcodei F.

2015

"White Paper on SMEs in Romania", Sigma, București

Cluster Management Guide – "Guidelines for the Development and Management of Cluster Initiatives",

Cloe project – www.clusterforum.org

www.greenenergycluster.ro

www.clusterobservatory.eu